

NUTRIENT EVALUATION OF SOME VARIETIES OF MAIZE STOVER RESIDUE GROWN WITHIN BAUCHI METROPOLIS

Ngele¹, M.B. Voncir², N., Neyu¹, A.P. and Zagi³ S.P.

¹Animal Production Programme, ²Crop Production Programme School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, P.M.B.0248, Bauchi, Bauchi State. ³Department of Agricultural Education, ³Directorate of Undergraduate Studies, College of Education, Azare, Bauchi state, Bauchi.

ABSTRACT

The research was conducted to evaluate the nutritive value of some maize variety residues in Bauchi metropolis. Maize stover of ten (10) varieties, Across 97, Oba super I, DMR-Y, Oba Tampa, Pop Csp, LNTR-Y, Gubi local, Sweet corn, Bauchi local and Manoma were collected from the Crop Production experimental farm immediately after the harvest of the primary crop. The maize residues were milled and analyzed for dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), crude fibre (CF), ether extract (EE) and ash. The number of leaves (NOS) and plant height (PH) were significant ($P<0.05$) across the varieties while, the leaf area (LA) was not influenced by variety. Number of leaves across the maize varieties ranged between 10.17 to 12.50 with, Across 97 having the highest value (12.50), and Oba super 1 and DMR-Y recording the least (10.17). Plant height (PH) ranged from 53.50 to 83.50 cm. Across 97 and LNTR-Y recorded the highest and lowest PH respectively. The nutrient composition showed that DM was significantly different ($P<0.05$) among the varieties with Oba Tampa having the highest value (97.99%) and Oba super I the least value (91.81%). CP, ash and organic matter (OM) were significantly not different among the varieties. The values ranged between 4.09% – 8.1%, 3.04% – 5.16% and 87.81% – 94.00% for CP, ash and OM respectively. CF was significantly different ($P<0.005$) with Pop Csp giving the highest value (50.41%) and Oba super I the least (34.87%). EE also showed a significant difference ($P<0.005$) among the maize varieties with values ranging between 0.74% and 1.50%. The results showed that Oba super 1 had the lowest CF and CP above the minimum required for rumen fermentation compared to the other varieties. Feeding of the other maize residue varieties requires been upgraded by appropriate treatment methods and/or supplementation to enhance effective utilization by livestock.

KEYWORDS: Nutrient, maize, variety, stover, evaluation, Bauchi.

INTRODUCTION

Crop residues are crop by-products which are left on the farm when the primary crop has been harvested. In Nigeria, cereals residues such as sorghum, maize, millet stovers and rice straws are the most important quantitatively. Leguminous or oil seed residues are produced in smaller quantities. They include groundnut, cowpea, soyabean and lab lab haulms. Increases in crop production due to increasing demand for staples will lead to production of more crop residues. As the conventional feedstuffs are very expensive because they are needed by both man and his farm animals, animal scientist and policy makers in the country should search for cheaper feed ingredients that can provide nutrients to livestock and poultry especially in a reasonable and affordable manner to most livestock farmers (Abubakar and Mohammed, 1992).

Feeding accounts for up to 70% of the cost of producing meat, milk and eggs. Feed supply is the basic resource of the industry. A number of non-conventional feedstuffs are currently under utilized. As conventional feedstuff such as the grains and pulses are also being consumed by human beings, they may not be available for raising livestock. The livestock industry is therefore increasingly being called upon to justify its existence as a hungry world raises the age old question: "Shall we have livestock feed or human food or have both?" (Abubakar, 1998). Inadequate supply of feed for livestock is the major setback to productivity in Nigeria, especially during the long dry season when the available pasture is low in quantity and quality. Most of these crop residues are low in crude protein (CP) which is below the minimum level of 7% CP required in forages to enhance voluntary intake, digestibility and utilization by ruminants (Smith, 1993). The utilization of the cheapest and most available feedstuff is a major challenge facing

livestock farmers in Nigeria amidst feed crisis (Bogoro, 1997). In terms of quantity, crop residues are presently the most important agricultural by-products available in the savanna belt of Nigeria of which Bauchi state is part (Bogoro, 1997). This study aimed at evaluating the nutritive value of ten (10) maize residue varieties grown within Bauchi environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The experiment was conducted at the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi the school farm of the School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, which is located west of the International Secondary School.

The experiment commenced during the cropping season in the month of July 6th, 2009 on a well drained, sandy loam soil. The experiment consisted of ten (10) maize varieties; Across 97, Oba super I, DMR-Y, Oba Tampa, Pop Csp, LNTR-Y, Gubi local, Sweet corn, Bauchi local and Manoma. They were laid in a complete randomized design (CRD) with two replications. Each plot had a size of 3x3m with a spacing of 75cm between the plots.

All varieties were sown two (2) seeds per stand which were later thinned to 1 (one) per stand at a spacing of 25 x 75cm intra and inter row. Manual weeding was carried out at 2nd and 6th weeks after germination. N. P. K fertilizer (20:10:10) was applied once at 6 weeks after germination. All the varieties were harvested after maturity in late October (25th October). The residues were collected immediately after harvest of the primary crop in replicate as planted in the field.

Chemical and Data analysis

The proximate composition of the ten (10) maize residue varieties were determined for dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), crude fibre (CF), ether extract (EE) and ash according to the method of AOAC (1980). Organic matter (OM) was determined as the difference between DM and ash. Data collection were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the general linear model (GLM) in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for windows, version 7.6 (SPSS, 1996). Significant means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) (Duncan, 1955).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The growth parameters (number of leaves, leaf area and plant height) are presented in Table 1. The number of leaves (NOL) across the maize varieties ranged between 10.17 to 12.50 which was, significantly ($P<0.05$) different across the varieties. Oba super 1 and DMR-Y recorded the lowest number of leaves (10.17 each) whereas, Across 97 had the highest number of leaves (12.50). The high number of leaves observed in Across 97 may have contributed to the high dry matter (DM) of the variety compared to others. This is clearly seen in Oba super 1 which has the lowest DM (91.81%) and the least number of leaves.

The leaf area (LA) measurement which was between 250.50 to 435.50 cm² was not significant across the maize varieties. However, the large leaf area observed in some of the maize varieties could be a compensatory effect for the fewer number of leaves in such varieties thereby, enhancing the process of photosynthesis in these varieties.

Plant height (PH) of the maize varieties was significant ($P<0.05$) with values ranging between 53.50 to 83.50 cm. Across 97 recorded the highest PH value (83.50 cm) while, LNTR-Y had the least (53.50 cm). The tallest plant observed in Across 97 may have contributed to its high number of leaves. Varieties with statistically similar plant heights such as Oba super 1, DMR-Y, LNTR-Y and Manoma also had similar number of leaves. This implies that the taller the plant, the more nodes for new leaf production.

Table 2 shows the proximate composition of the maize residue varieties; dry matter (DM), crude protein (CP), crude fibre (CF), ash and ether extract (EE). The result shows that Oba Tampa variety had the highest dry matter (97.99%) which was not significantly different ($P<0.05$) from the other varieties except Oba super I which had the lowest dry matter content (91.81%). The 97.99% recorded for Oba super I agrees with Agreheore, (1996) who reported a dry matter content of 96.0% for maize cob. The value of

Oba super I (91.81%) also agree with an earlier value of 92.2% for maize straw (Alhassan, 1989). That of Pop Csp (94.09%) agrees with Bogoro *et al.*, (2006) who reported 93.9% for maize stover.

Crop residues are generally characterized by low crude protein (CP) content. There was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the crude protein content among varieties. However, Oba super I had the highest crude protein content of 8.12%. The CP content for Bauchi local variety (5.29%) agrees with Bogoro *et al.*, (2006) who reported a CP content of 4.7% for maize stover.

Crude fibre (CF) of the crop residues was generally high. The crude fibre values ranged between 34.87% and 50.41%. Oba super I variety had the lowest CF (34.87%) and Pop Csp highest (50.41%) which could be as a result of varietal differences. The rest of the varieties were not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). DMR-Y variety recorded a value of 45.25% which agrees with Alhassan *et al.* (1986) and MAFF, (1984) who reported 46.2% and 46.1% CF for maize straw respectively.

Ether extract (EE) result showed that Oba super I variety had the highest (1.50%) and LNTR-Y lowest (0.44%) while the other varieties were not significantly different. The 1.50% EE of Oba super I agrees with Moss *et al.* (1994) who reported 1.50% for barley straw and McDonald *et al.* (1998) who reported 1.50% EE for wheat straw.

There was no significant difference for ash among varieties. However, Gubi local with 5.16% recorded the highest ash value which agrees with McDonald *et al.*, (1998) and MAFF, (1984) who reported 5-3% ash for barley straw and 5.6% ash for maize straw respectively.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that maize varieties differ in their composition. Oba super I, seem better with the highest crude protein value (8.12%) and lowest crude fibre (34.87%) across the varieties. It has more than the minimum crude protein (7%) required for enhancing rumen fermentation. However, for efficient utilization of these residues as dry season feed for ruminant livestock, requires that they be upgraded by treatment methods or supplementation to enhance effective utilization.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, M.M. (1998). Utilization of convectional feedstuff for sustainable livestock production. Inaugural lecture Series No. 9. Abubakar Tafawa Balewa university, Bauchi, 30th march, 1998.
- Abubakar, M.M. and Mohammed, I. (1992). Utilization of slaughter house byproducts for sustainable livestock production in Nigeria. In: Ojo, J.A.T (ed.) Mobilizing Finance for Natural Resources Conservation in Nigeria, Abuja. Natural resources Conservation Council. Pp. 193-201.
- Agreheore, M.(1996). Voluntary intake and nutrient digestibility of crop residue based rations for goats and sheep. *Small Ruminant Research*, 22: 7-12.
- Alhassan, W.S. (1989). Crop residue utilization with special reference to pastoral production. In: J.O. Gefu, I.F.Adu, E.A. Lufadeju, M.S. Kallah and M.O. Awogbade (eds.). Pastoralism in Nigeria: Past, present and future. NAPRI, Shika. Pp. 70-94.
- Alhassan, W.S., Ehoche, O.W. and Adu, I.F. (1986). Influence of graded levels of cotton seed cake supplementation on the nutritive value of cereal straws fed to sheep and goats. *Journal of Animal Production Research*, 6(1): 39-53.
- A.O.A.C. (1980). Official Method of Analysis (13th edition). Association of Official Analytical Chemist, AOAC, Washington DC, USA.
- Bogoro, S.E.S. (1997). Effect of protein-energy supplementation on rumen kinetics, metabolic profile and growth performance of rams fed high fibre diets. PhD Thesis, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

Bogoro, S., Kalla, D.J.U and Fomukong, B. (2006). Chemical composition and In situ rumen degradability of blood meal and urea-treated crop residue. *Nigerian Journal of Experimental and Applied Biology*, 7(1): 27-35.

Duncan, D.B. (1955). Multiple range and multiple F-tests. *Biometrics*, 11: 1-42.

MAFF (1984). Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food. Department of Agriculture for Scotland and Department of Agriculture for Northern Ireland. Energy allowances and feeding system for ruminants. Reference Book 433, HMSO, London.

McDonald, P., Edwards, R.A., Greenhalgh, J.E.D. and Morgan, C.A. (1998). *Animal Nutrition*, 5th Edition, Pearson Educational Ltd., UK. Pp.142-176.

Moss, A.R., Givens, D.I. and Gernasworth, P.C. (1994). The effect of alkali treatment of cereal straws on digestibility and methane production by sheep. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 49: 245-259.

Smith, O.B. (1993). Feed resources for intensive smallholder system in the tropics. The role of crop residue. Proceedings of the 17th International Grassland Congress, Australia/ New Zealand, 18-21st February, 1993, Vol., 111, 1969-1976.

SPSS (1996). Statistical Package for Social Sciences. SPSS/STAT Version 7.5 for windows.

Table 1: Effect of variety on number of leaves (NOL), leaf area (LA) and plant height (PH).

Variety	Number of leaves (NOL)	Leaf area (LA) (cm ²)	Plant height (PH) (cm).
Across 97	12.50 ^a	304.30	83.50 ^a
Oba super 1	10.17 ^c	277.67	53.83 ^c
DMR-Y	10.17 ^c	435.50	63.67 ^{bc}
Ola Tampa	11.17 ^{bc}	376.83	73.17 ^{ab}
Pop CsP	11.00 ^{bc}	261.50	72.83 ^{ab}
LNTR-Y	11.00 ^{bc}	250.50	53.50 ^c
Gubi local	11.33 ^b	310.83	69.83 ^{ab}
Sweet corn	11.50 ^{ab}	277.50	77.67 ^{ab}
Bauchi local	11.17 ^{bc}	317.67	72.50 ^{ab}
Manoma	11.00 ^{bc}	297.83	68.00 ^{abc}
SEM	0.35	76.27	5.10
LOS	*	NS	*

^{a,b,c}Means within a column with different superscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05); NS= Not significant; SEM= Standard error of mean; LOS= Level of significant.

Table 2: Proximate composition of some maize stover varieties Composition (%)

Maize varieties	DM	CP	CF	EE	ASH	OM	
Across 97	97.31 ^{ab}		4.27	43.45 ^{ab}	0.93 ^{ab}	3.88	93.43
Oba super I	91.81 ^b		8.12	34.87 ^b	1.50 ^a	3.94	87.87
DMR – Y	94.84 ^{ab}		6.07	45.25 ^{ab}	1.01 ^{ab}	3.04	91.80
Oba Tampa	97.99 ^a		5.61	47.74 ^a	0.83 ^{ab}	3.99	94.00
Pop CsP	94.09 ^{ab}	4.09	50.41 ^a	0.91 ^{ab}	4.59	89.50	
LNTR – Y	95.75 ^{ab}		4.31	48.72 ^a	0.44 ^b	4.30	91.45
Gubi local	94.40 ^{ab}	4.33	49.38 ^a	0.86 ^{ab}	5.16	89.24	
Sweet corn	94.24 ^{ab}		6.3	49.07 ^a	0.79 ^{ab}	3.79	90.45
Bauchi local	96.11 ^{ab}		5.29	49.84 ^a	1.27 ^{ab}	4.22	91.89
Manoma	95.95 ^{ab}	5.61	49.48 ^a	0.74 ^{ab}	3.94	92.01	
SEM	1.62		1.64	3.76	0.26	0.86	-
LOS	*		NS	*	*	NS	-

^{a,b}Means within a column with different superscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05); NS= Not significant; SEM= Standard error of mean; LOS= Level of significant., DM= dry matter, CP= Crude protein, CF= Crude fibre, EE= Ether extract, OM= Organic matter.

Received for Publication: 14/11/2011

Accepted for Publication: 02/01/2012

Corresponding author

Ngele, M.B.

Animal Production Programme, School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Abubakar Tafawa
Balewa University, P.M.B.0248, Bauchi, Bauchi State.

Email: mbngele2000@yahoo.com